

WOMEN AND CHURCH DEVELOPMENT: A CASE STUDY OF C.W.O. IN MBAITOLI AREA OF IMO STATE

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Abstract

It is a known fact that right from the early times, women have been playing significant roles in the church and the society at large. However, in spite of their enormous contributions, their activities are under- estimated, scarcely documented and recognized. This is as a result of our society being male chauvinistic. The objective of this research work is to appreciate the roles/contributions of the Catholic Women Organization in church development in Mbaitoli. It is also aimed at documenting their contributions both in the church and in the society. Qualitative methodology was used in this work which combines both primary (oral interviews and participant observations) and the secondary sources such as textbooks, journals, web materials etcetera. The women organization no doubt play more roles than any other group in the church and this is indisputable. However, when the women and their activities are adequately recognized and documented, they will contribute more to the growth and development of the church and this will in turn have more positive impact both on the church and society at large.

Keywords: Women, Church, Development, CWO, Society.

Introduction

It is an incontrovertible fact that right from the primal period, women have been playing essential roles both in the family and in the society. They are involved in the political, economic, social and even religious spheres of life. We cannot in a twinkle of an eye forget the sterling and noble roles played by the Biblical Esther, Judith, Deborah, Virgin Mary and other women in human and societal development. Unfortunately, these roles have not been accorded the desired pride of place in the

scheme of things by the society as a result of it being male chauvinistic. The church also cannot absolutely absolve itself from this unfair treatment of women. The activities and roles of the women are under-estimated, scarcely documented and recognized as if there is nothing remarkable about the Christian- Women and their activities. Both Anyanwu (2000: 116) and Adesina (2000: p.187) affirm that women were not recognized. In the same vein, Nkemdirim (1995:187) lamented the disregard for women and their roles. Writing on a similar situation, Daniel Denga of the University of Calabar, observes that awareness of the significant role being played by women----is definitely lagging behind...(Ada,1997).

This work is therefore, going to x-ray the roles and impacts of women in church development using the Catholic women organization in Mbaitoli as its focal point. Although in the Catholic Church, the Mary League Girls' Association, Block Rosary crusade and other groups contribute in church growth and development. However, this work is focused on the catholic women Organization because they contribute more in church growth and development and this is indisputable.

Definition of Basic Concepts

Women

The Webster's Universal Dictionary & Thesaurus (2005) defined women as an adult human female. This definition was corroborated by the Collins Cobuild English Dictionary (2001) which describes women as adult female human being. However, we can describe women as matured adult human beings of the feminine gender. They may be wives, mothers, mistress, religious (Revered sisters or mothers or Nun) and so on.

Church

The word "church" according to Akpunonu (in Ukpong, Okure, Anyanwu, Okeke, Odoemene (eds) (1992:p. 28) is a community gathered by the father in the Son through the spirit to proclaim the wonders of God and the salvation of humanity performed by Jesus Christ, God – man dead and risen. It is derived from the Greek word "ekklesia" which denotes a gathering, an assembly, a congregation, probably of citizens summoned together by a herald. We succinctly defined a church as a community gathered by the father in the Son through the spirit to proclaim the wonders of God and the salvation of humanity performed by Jesus Christ, God-man, dead and risen. Iroegbu (1996:44) did not differ from Akpunonu as he described the church as the community of believers in the Trinitarian God, gathered together and commissioned by Jesus Christ, God- man to continue the mission- the establishment of God's reign in the world until he returns at the end of life. Onwubiko (1999:p.76) while given a working understanding of the concept "Church" it as a community of faithful people in Christ mysteriously sustained by

the Holy Spirit in the communion of the father and the Son. Wotogbe- Weneka (2004: p. 20) summarily defined the church as a body of believers in Christ. Although the magnificent edifices we see all over the place can also be referred to as churches but in a miniature sense. We can therefore, see a church as people who believes in the Trinitarian God, who are redeemed by Christ through his death on the cross and who are united by the holy spirit. As a result, they share in the sonship of Christ and therefore, heirs of the kingdom of God.

Development

Development is a subject matter that embraces many spheres of life- social, political, economic, psychological and spiritual. To this end, Ogungbamila sees development as referring to qualitative rise in skill, capacity, freedom, self discipline, responsibility and creativity which is geared towards physical, material and or psychological well being. Narrowing his assertion down to the religious angle, he argues that development stipulates that the society and the individual move progressively from a primitive to a better way of communicating with the Supreme Being (Ifeanacho, 2006:p.96). To Akinsaya, development implies sustainable growth, poverty, reduction, institutional transformation (Ifeanacho, 2006:p. 105). We can simply define development as a more efficient and more progressive way of doing things than what existed before. However, for the purpose of this work, we shall define development as the sustainable growth, progress and expansion of the church.

C.W.O.

C.W.O. is an acronym for the Catholic Women Organization. It is an organization that unites Catholic Women. Although unwedded catholic women are still members, they do not have the same rights and privileges as their wedded counterparts. The aims and of the C.W.O. include inter alia', unifying all catholic women under one umbrella, fostering the spirit of love, contributing meaningfully to the development and growth of the church and so on. (Justina Dike, personal communications: August 16, 2025).

Brief History of C.W.O. in Mbaitoli

The Catholic Women Organization was established and first inaugurated in Nigeria on the 5th of May, 1964 in Onitsha Archdiocese by the Late Archbishop Charles Heerey C.S.Sp (info@stgeraldgbagada.org). With the inauguration of the national body, the C.W.O got to Owerri Diocese (as Owerri was then a suffragan Diocese of Onitsha Ecclesiastical province). It was from the Owerri Diocesan C.W.O. that Mbaitoli evolved (Mbaitoli is part of Owerri Diocese then now Archdiocese).

Today, the Catholic Women Organisation operates in the twenty nine parishes and four special jurisdictions currently in Mbaitoli.

It was from Emekuku that the organization reached Mbaitoli. Today, the C.W.O. operates in the twenty one parishes currently in Mbaitoli.

The Impact/Roles of C.W.O. in Church Development in Mbaitoli

The roles and impacts of the C.W.O. in church development cannot be over-emphasized and they are indispensable in the church. Lending weight to the above assertion Rev. Fr. Gerald Nnaocha (personal communications: July 25, 2025) said that without the mothers, the church is bound to experience crises, hence numerically they are very high and financially, their contributions are wonderful.

In the area of ecclesiastical development, the Catholic Women are up and doing. It is the C.W.O. that feed the priests working in the various parishes in Mbaitoli. They contribute both money and foodstuffs for the feeding, maintenance and up-keep of these priests. The C.W.O. also plays major roles when the priests in the parishes hold recollections or even celebrate their birthday or priestly ordination anniversary. It is always the C.W.O. that contribute the chunk of what is used. They cook, feed and serve the guests in such ceremonies. In the same vein, the seminarians on Apostolic work benefit from the largesse of the C.W.O. They are catered for by the respective parish C.W.Os. The C.W.O. in Mbaitoli visits the seminaries in Owerri Archdiocese and donates cash, foodstuffs and other material items. The Catholic Women Organisation, also fight water scarcity in and around their various parish compounds. For example, the St. Joseph's C.W.O. Ifakala, St. Theresa's C.W.O. Ochii Ogwa sank bore holes in their respective parishes for the priests and parishioners' use. Some have constructed and mounted items of devotion. A case in point is the St. Patrick's C.W.O.- Ogwa constructed and installed the magnificent Grotto of the Blessed Virgin Mary at the parish centre for prayers, meditation et cetera. (Ugwulebo 2012: p. 173). In many parishes, the C.W.O. constructed, equipped and furnished boys' quarters and kitchens in the parish centre for the priests' use. Also, in the area under study, the C.W.O. in some parishes bought and donated official cars to their parish priests to enable them carry out their work hitch-free. It is no longer news that many parish C.W.Os bought and installed generating sets for their church and priests' use. The C.W.O. also engages in spiritual works of praying for the sick, especially their members. As loving and caring mothers, the members of the C.W.O visit the Orphans, motherless babies, poor and needy, offering gifts and prayers for them. They are not only involved in the above activities, the members also attend their first Saturday masses, May and October devotions et cetera. Apart from providing free physical labour and money for church projects such as church buildings, parish house, office, chapels among other projects, the C.W.O also feed the labourers and the church workers. The C.W.O has made tremendous impact in the cleanliness of their various church compounds and their surroundings. Regularly, they clean and tidy up church

buildings and premises. This justifies the saying that "cleanliness is next to godliness. They also assist in decorating the Altar for Liturgical services.

Since nobody toys with security, in some parishes, the C.W.O fenced the residence of their priests to enhance the security of lives and properties. Equally, the C.W.O is involved in erosion control. In some parishes visited in the course of this work, we saw how the C.W.O invested enormous sums of money in erosion control in and around their church premises, hence one of the women boasted that "what the men could not do, we have done it (Ugwulebo,2012: p.174).

On the economic side, the C.W.Os in Mbaitoli have also made their marks. Some parish C.W.Os built and rented out stores to people, thereby generating revenue for them. They also engage in the sale of sacramentals and other church items. All the parish C.W.Os contributed immensely in the establishment of the Chikum Microfinance Bank of Owerri Archdiocese. The C.W.O also make profit from their Bazaar sales as there is no established case of loss during C.W.O. Bazaar sales. Therefore, the money realized from the Bazaar sales is ploughed back into the organization's treasury. In some parishes, the C.W.O rent out canopies, pots, seats, chairs, table, and spoons to people who need them at a cost, thereby improving their economic fortune. On the other hand, parish C.W.Os assist their mass-servers, Mary league girls, Catholic youths and others in meeting their financial obligations both at the parish and Archdiocesan levels. Similarly, the C.W.O give loans to some of their poor members to engage in one business or the other, thereby developing them economically. When these Catholic women are economically developed, the church benefits, because they will meet up with their financial obligations in the church and the society at large.

Socio- culturally, the Catholic women organizations in Mbaitoli have not played the second fiddle. They are at war against the obnoxious socio-cultural practices which dehumanizes the human person. They are engaged in fighting such widowhood practices as using broken bottles or blunt razor blade to shave the hair of a bereaved Christian woman, forcing a widow to drink the water used in washing the corpse of the late husband. They also expand their armours in waging wars against female genital mutilation, early girl- child marriage, human battering, the Osu caste system among other ills. It is not only in waging wars that they occupy their time with, the C.W.O also reconcile members, settle disputes between husbands and wives et cetera.

In the area of educational development, the Catholic women are not left out both collectively and individually. The women believe that true success in life depends on good hard work, serious mindedness and decent living. On this ground, the C.W.O encourages proper training of children who are the future leaders. To actualize this, in some parishes in the area, the C.W.O established and maintain pre-

nursery, primary and secondary schools. However, in some parishes where the C.W.O. could not establish their own school, they support the church established schools materially, financially and morally. For instance, in Orodo, the StellaMaris C.W.O. built and equipped the StellaMaris Secondary school's Home Economics laboratory. Besides,, the .women organize and facilitate seminars and workshops for their members where participants are exposed to burning issues such as same sex, marriage, abortion, HIV/AIDS. Kidnapping, female genital mutilation, drug abuse, importance of female education and so on.

Problem Militating Against the Activities of the C.W.O in Mbaitoli

The Catholic Women Organization in Mbaitoli just like any other human organization is not immuned from problems. Some of the problems bedeviling the organization include inadequate finance, poor and unsound economic base of some members, polygamy, Lukewarm and non-chalant attitude of members, how degree of assistance and co-operation from the various parishes pastoral councils, factionalism, inefficient "and corrupt leadership including high death rate of members among the numerous problem confronting the organization.

Summary

In this paper, we have endeavoured to define the-basic concepts in this work and they are women, church, development and C.W.O. This is for easy understanding of the issue under study. We took a brief journey into the history of the C.W.O in Mbaitoli. The roles and impacts of the C.W.O. in Mbaitoli were widely discussed since it is the crux of the matter. We found out that the women are indispensable in the church. They assist the church financially and otherwise. They cater for the priests, religious, seminarians, church workers and labourers who work in the church. They in some cases sank boreholes, bought generating sets in the Church. They also engage in economic ventures which help them to raise money to contribute to church growth and development. Socio-culturally, the C.W.O is engaged in fighting obnoxious socio-cultural practices which dehumanizes the human person. The women made impact in the area of educational development in Mbaitoli. On the other hand, since no society is immuned from problems, the C.W.O is therefore no exception. Some of the problems of the organization include inadequate fund, high death rate of members. Factionalism, inefficient and corrupt leadership among other problems confronting them.

Recommendations

It is our recommendation that the C.W.O should be given a pride of place, due recognition and be appreciated both by the church and the society at large. The activities of the Catholic Women Organization should be documented as we could

not see any real documented evidence of the C.W.O and its activities in all the parishes in Mbaitoli.

The C.W.O in Mbaitoli should engage in more economic ventures to boost their financial base. They should engage in Garri processing, pure and bottled water production since they are the booming business in Imo State in recent times. They should also engage in aggressive farming since Mbaitoli has arable lands.

The C.W.O should organize holiday programmes for children and youths in the various parishes in Mbaitoli. This will help in keeping the children busy and engaged during their holiday and also help in checking their ills.

The C.W.O should purge itself of bad, inefficient and corrupt leaders. Only good disciplined, efficient, tasted and trusted women should be given portfolios in the C.W.O. This will help in taking the organization to greater heights.

Conclusion

From the foregoing analysis, it is a variety that the catholic Women Organization in Mbaitoli has paid its dues as far as church growth and development is concerned. Without the women, the church is bound to experience unpardonable crisis and problems as their population is very high and financially and morally they contribute more to church development and this is indisputable. However, the male folk should encourage the women so that they can contribute more to church growth and development.

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